

Supplementary Materials

Table S1. Indirect, direct and total effects in fiber yield in each genotype and in the environmental index.

	FYG1	FYG2	FYG3	FYG4	FYG5	FYG6	FYG7	FYG8	FYG9	FYG10	FYG11	FYG12	I
$\hat{Y}_{TS \rightarrow I}$	869.71	726.24	1,211.77	739.02	559.45	345.50	1,235.10	737.43	1,000.73	414.74	628.60	1,082.97	-
$\hat{Y}_{T2M \rightarrow I}$	-679.49	-567.40	-946.74	-577.39	-437.09	-269.90	-964.90	-576.15	-781.86	-324.03	-491.12	-846.12	-
$\hat{Y}_{RH2M \rightarrow I}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\hat{Y}_{WS2M_MAX \rightarrow I}$	351.06	293.15	489.14	298.31	225.82	139.40	498.50	297.67	403.95	167.41	253.74	437.15	-
$\hat{Y}_{PRECTOTCORR \rightarrow I}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\hat{Y}_{CLRSKY_SFC_PAR_TOT \rightarrow I}$	-60.42	-50.45	-84.19	-51.34	-38.87	-24.00	-85.80	-51.23	-69.52	-28.81	-43.67	-75.24	-
$\hat{Y}_{TS}$	-	-	-636.36	-	-	541.66	-354.86	666.40	-550.7	646.60	-	-	795.90
$\hat{Y}_{T2M}$	-	-	490.07	-	-	-455.39	389.41	-622.49	538.30	-	-	-	-621.90
$\hat{Y}_{RH2M}$	-	-	-30.01	-	-	-	-	42.61	-	-	-	20.84	-
$\hat{Y}_{WS2M_MAX}$	-	-	-	-	-	135.71	-118.73	-	-	212.70	-	-	321.30
$\hat{Y}_{PRECTOTCORR}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	14.80	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\hat{Y}_{CLRSKY_SFC_PAR_TOT}$	-	-	30.17	-	-	-25.02	46.06	-	-	-	-	-	-55.30
$\hat{Y}_{TS} + \hat{\beta}_{1i}^{SEM} \hat{Y}_{TS \rightarrow I}$	869.71	726.24	575.41	739.02	559.45	887.11	882.20	1,403.84	450.05	1,061.36	628.60	1,082.97	-
$\hat{Y}_{T2M} + \hat{\beta}_{1i}^{SEM} \hat{Y}_{T2M \rightarrow I}$	-679.49	-567.40	-456.68	-577.39	-437.09	-725.29	-575.53	-1,198.65	-243.58	-324.03	-491.12	-846.12	-
$\hat{Y}_{RH2M} + \hat{\beta}_{1i}^{SEM} \hat{Y}_{RH2M \rightarrow I}$	-	-	-30.01	-	-	-	-	42.61	-	-	-	20.84	-
$\hat{Y}_{WS2M_MAX} + \hat{\beta}_{1i}^{SEM} \hat{Y}_{WS2M_MAX \rightarrow I}$	351.06	293.15	489.14	298.31	225.82	275.15	379.81	297.67	403.95	380.16	253.74	437.15	-
$\hat{Y}_{PRECTOTCORR} + \hat{\beta}_{1i}^{SEM} \hat{Y}_{PRECTOTCORR \rightarrow I}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	14.80	-	-	-	-	-	-
$\hat{Y}_{CLRSKY_SFC_PAR_TOT} + \hat{\beta}_{1i}^{SEM} \hat{Y}_{CLRSKY_SFC_PAR_TOT \rightarrow I}$	-60.42	-50.45	-54.02	-51.34	-38.87	-49.02	-39.74	-51.23	-69.52	-28.81	-43.67	-75.24	-

FYG: Average fiber yield of each genotype (1, 2, ..., 12); TS: Earth Skin Temperature; T2M: Temperature at 2 Meters; RH2M: Relative Humidity at 2 Meters; WS2M_MAX: Wind Speed at 2 Meters Maximum; PRECTOTCORR: Precipitation Corrected; CLRSKY_SFC_PAR_TOT: Clear Sky Surface Photosynthetically Active Radiation Total; I: Environmental Index. Gen1: TMG 41 WS; Gen2: TMG 43 WS; Gen3: IMA CV 690; Gen4: IMA 5675 B2RF; Gen5: IMA 08 WS; Gen6: NUOPAL; Gen7: DP 555 BGRR; Gen8: DELTA OPAL; Gen9: BRS 286; Gen10: BRS 335; Gen11: BRS 368 RF; Gen 12: BRS 369 RF.